

QUEUE THEORETIC APPROACH TO ANALYZE COMMUNICATION NETWORKS IN INDIAN SMART CITIES

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Abstract

This study aims to analyse the congestion dynamics of the communication networks in the context of the smart cities of India with regard to changing infrastructural / technological scenario. The Indian smart city of Aligarh has been selected for study. The queueing model (M/M/1); a single server model with poisson arrival and exponential processing time distribution, has been used to analyse the communication system at different locations in the city. Various performance measures, such as utilisation, number of packets in the system, time spent by a packet in the system, latency and packet loss, have been determined and analysed.

Keywords: Communication Network, Smart City, Performance Measures, Latency, Packet loss.

Introduction

Queueing theory is a branch of mathematics that falls under mathematical modeling. The theory sprang up on the verge of the 20th century, with the application to telephone communication systems. Since then, it has been playing a significant role in studying and analysing a lot of problems that we encounter in our real lives. It understands the congestion phenomenon deeply, interprets models for systematic study, predicts and provides remedial solutions.

A **Queue**, is referred to a collection or group of customers who arrive at the service facility for a particular type of service.

(Queueing / Communication System)

Communication Network: refers to a collection of multiple queues and each queue consists of data packets waiting for transmission at different terminal nodes, connected via links. Thus, by nature and functioning, the communication network can be identified as a queueing system. With the advancement of science and technology and the population explosion, the data generation rate is going on multiplying rapidly. That's why its management (handling, control, manipulation) requires:

(i) Pace-keeping with emerging technologies

(ii) to be updated, having delved into the phenomenon and then needs optimization in accordance with the changing scenario.

In the context of Indian smart cities, the rapidly evolving landscape of urbanisation and communication technology has raised the question of how to dig into and model a communication network to optimise the different measures related to functional efficiency. Queueing theory can adequately answer this question.

To answer this question, a single server queueing model (M/M/1), with Poisson arrival and an exponential service pattern, has been used to understand the communication system and the related measures.

Essential terms and symbols:

The important terms and symbols used in the study are as under –

λ : data packets arrival / generation rate / throughput

μ : data transmission / processing rate

L_q : average number of data packets waiting for transmission / processing

L_s : average number of data packets in system (in waiting and in processing)

W_q : the average time spent by a data packet in queue (waiting)

W_s : the average time spent by a data packet in system (in queue + in service)

Key Concepts:

The essential concepts used in the study have been described briefly as follows:

Little's formula: This formula is a benchmark in the theory of queues, was propounded by Little in 1961. It interrelates the number of packets in queue / system and the time spent by a

data packet in the queue or system. Mathematically, this formula is defined in a precise manner; thus,

$$L = \lambda w$$

Server utilisation: server utilisation is defined as the product of throughput and packet processing time. It is denoted by ρ , then,

$$\rho = \frac{\lambda}{\mu}$$

Latency: In communication networks, latency refers to the time that a data packet takes to move from the source to the sink (destination).

Data/packet loss: refers to the number of packets sent but not received, i.e., the data packets transferred over the network but could not be processed.

Literature Review:

Queueing theory emerged on the verge of the twentieth century with the applications in telephone communication systems. Since then, it has been a linchpin and backbone of this field and is going on spreading over other numerous fields of our day-to-day lives. It has attracted the attention of scientists, engineers, mathematicians and pioneers in varied fields. A brief survey of relevant and important researches that have been carried out in the field under context, is as follows:

2018 Daradkeh et al. (2018) studied the communication system, emphasising the quality of service. They revealed the fact that the parameters—channel capacity, buffering, routing and load balance—play a significant role in improving the quality of service. That's why their optimisation needs special attention and proper management. **Yang and Zhang (2018)** looked deeper into queueing models in the context of urban communication networks and suggested mechanisms and protocols to fight against the threats that the communication network normally encounters. **Li and Wang (2019)** studied queueing models in the special context of the challenges that we face in smart cities due to the rapid change in their urban landscapes. In this study, they emphasised the need to pay special attention to manage and optimize the factors of traffic load connectivity and emerging technologies while modelling communication systems in smart cities. **Kumar et al. (2020)** delved into urban communication networks and investigated that edge computing technologies are being proven to be more effective in improving different performance measures of the communication network under context. **Chen et al. (2021)** found in their study that the mobility of individuals in smart cities affects the performance of the communication system to a

Table – 1 For Peak hours (5.30 pm to 9.30 pm)

Location	Packet arrival rate, per second: λ	Packet Processing rate, per second: μ
Janakpuri	16	24
Centre Point	12	20
Railway Road	10	15
Achal Taal	8	12
Exhibition area	10	16

Table – 2 Non-Peak hours (12.30 pm to 3.30 pm)

Location	Packet arrival rate, per second: λ	Packet Processing rate, per second: μ
Janakpuri	10	24
Centre Point	9	20
Railway Road	9	15
Achal Taal	8	12
Exhibition area	8	16

Table – 3 Data for latency and Packet loss:

Location	For Peak hours (5.30 pm to 9.30 pm)		Non-Peak hours (12.30 pm to 3.30 pm)	
	Latency (ms)	Packet loss (%)	Latency (ms)	Packet Loss (%)
Janakpuri	25	3.5	16	2
Centre Point	24	3.4	14	1.9
Railway Road	21	3.2	19	3.00
Achal Taal	19	3.0	17	2.9
Exhibition area	18	2.9	12	.9

Calculation of packets in the system and time spent by a packet: These measures have been calculated in Tables 4 and 5 for the peak and non-peak hours, respectively.

Table – 4 For Peak-hours (5.30 pm to 9.30 pm)

Location	Utilization ρ	Average time (second) spent by a packet in system: W_s	Average packets in system: L_s
Janakpuri	.66	.125	2
Centre Point	.6	.125	1.5
Railway Road	.66	.20	2
Achal Taal	.66	.25	2
Exhibition area	.63	.166	1.66

Table – 5 For Non-Peak hours (5.30 pm to 9.30 pm)

Location	Utilization ρ	Average time (second) spent by a packet in system: W_s	Average packets in system: L_s
Janakpuri	.416	.071	.71
Centre Point	.45	.09	.81
Railway Road	.6	.166	1.5
Achal Taal	.66	.25	2
Exhibition area	.5	.125	1

Concluding Discussion :

In Table 4, 5 performance measures—utilisation (ρ), time spent by a data packet in the system, (W_s) and number of packets in the system at any time (L_s) are calculated using the formulae given in the appendix. Table 3 provides the latency and percentage of packet loss. From these tables, it is evident that:

- (i) If the processing rate is constant, the time spent by a packet in the system and the number of packets are directly proportional to the arrival rate.
- (ii) Achal Taal and Railway Road areas remain overloaded with the deployed servers.
- (iii) Janakpuri, the centre point and exhibition areas are overloaded during peak-hours.
- (iv) The locations having higher latency have higher packet loss.
- (v) The packets spend more time in the system during peak-hours as compared to non-peak hours.
- (vi) The number of packets in the system during peak-hours is greater than the number of packets during non-peak hours.

Assumptions/limitations: The study has been made under the following assumptions and limitations:.

- (i) The network has been supposed to attain a steady state.
- (ii) Packet size is supposed to be uniform.
- (iii) The network is supposed to be an M/M/1 queueing model.
- (iv) The findings can't be used directly for other locations or cities since different cities have different infrastructure and technologies.

Conclusion:

Communication is a linchpin for the all-round development of our society. It enhances quality of life by increasing capability and the ability of doing better to achieve the expected goals. But it requires good coordination among the planners, executives and executors to develop the appropriate infrastructure while keeping pace with the emerging technologies, i.e., we would have to establish a happy medium between the arrival pattern and the performance efficiency of the system.

Appendix

This Appendix includes the Formulae Employed to calculate different measures

Formulae,

- Server utilization, $\rho = \frac{\lambda}{\mu}$
- Little's formula, $L = \lambda W$
- Average number of packets in the system, $L_s = \frac{\rho}{1-\rho}$
- Average number of packets in buffer (queue), $L_q = \frac{\rho^2}{1-\rho}$
- Time spent by the packet in system, $W_s = \frac{1}{\mu(1-\rho)}$
- Time spent by the packet in waiting, $W_q = \frac{\rho}{\mu(1-\rho)}$

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